

How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates

The vast majority of searches for EPOC reviews are conducted by one of our Information Specialists. However it remains important that authors are aware of the principles involved in accurate search reporting. To assist authors in recording and reporting search methods we have developed the following standardized language and format. While unique to EPOC, the wording and format agree with the major components of the [Cochrane Handbook](#) of Systematic Reviews, the [Cochrane Style Guide](#), [MECIR](#) (Methodological Expectations for Cochrane Intervention Reviews) Standards for the Reporting of Cochrane Intervention Reviews and the [PRISMA-S checklist](#).

Questions regarding reporting of search methods should be directed to the Cochrane Information Specialist (CIS) assigned to your protocol, review, or update.

General advice on recording search methodology in order to facilitate clear reporting

1. All searches

- 1.1. It is essential that all search strategies for all sources are recorded, **this includes search terms used to search websites and grey literature sources**. Search strategies must be recorded "as run", if possible, showing the numbers of results line by line.
- 1.2. Please use a 'search log' to record database names, database provider, numbers of results identified and date of search. An empty search audit spreadsheet can be found in the [EPOC resources for review authors](#). A completed version of the spreadsheet will be sent to authors by the Information Specialist completing a search or search update
- 1.3. Please report whether or not the search strategies have been peer reviewed.

2. Protocols

- 2.1. Only one search strategy is required for publication of a protocol. Typically, this is the MEDLINE strategy. However, if other strategies have been developed, these may also be reported.
- 2.2. Please paste the protocol search strategy in an appendix, not in the main text.

3. Reviews and updates

- 3.1. To report the search process, please use the EPOC search methods template text in the next section.
- 3.2. All search strategies, including grey literature, trial registries, websites and citation searches, should be included in an appendix. If possible they should be reported "as run" in other words with line numbers and line counts included.
- 3.3. Resources used for grey literature and trial registry searches should be listed and the URLs should be provided.

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

- 3.4. For “hand searched” journals, please document the title of the journal and the issues searched. Please indicate your method of “hand searching” – if you searched the journals electronically, please report the terms used in the search appendix.
- 3.5. If search strategies have changed since publication of the protocol an explanation should be provided under the review heading: “Differences between protocol and review”. Check with your Cochrane Information Specialist for guidance on what information to include.
- 3.6. Please add the number of items found and screened to a [PRISMA](#) flow diagram, and report this information in an appendix. The EPOC Information Specialist assigned to your review can provide information on numbers of results per source searched and numbers of duplicates removed. **It is the authors’ responsibility to keep track of all other numbers relating to the PRISMA flow diagram and ensure they are reported accurately.**

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

PROTOCOLS

Where in the protocol?	Main text
<p>All protocols will have this text as these are the core databases and trials registries that comply with MECIR.</p> <p>Ensure the appendix is linked.</p>	<p>Search methods for identification of studies</p> <p>Electronic searches</p> <p>The EPOC Information Specialist will develop the search strategies in consultation with the review authors.</p> <p>We will search the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) and Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) for related systematic reviews. We will search the following databases for primary studies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), in the Cochrane Library • MEDLINE Ovid • Embase Ovid • <i>etc</i> <p>Search strategies will comprise natural language and controlled vocabulary terms. We will not apply any limits on language or publication date. We will use a methodology search filter to limit retrieval to appropriate study designs. See Appendix 1 for the MEDLINE search strategy, which we will adapt for searching other databases.</p> <p>Searching other resources</p> <p>Trial registries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHO ICTRP (World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform); trialsearch.who.int/ • US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register, ClinicalTrials.gov; clinicaltrials.gov/
<p>All protocols will have some of this text.</p> <p>Edit as appropriate.</p>	<p>Grey literature</p> <p>We will search the grey literature to identify studies not indexed in the databases listed above.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source, URL • Source, URL • <i>etc</i> <p>We will also review reference lists of all included studies and relevant systematic reviews for additional potentially eligible primary studies. We will contact authors of included studies and reviews to clarify reported published information, and to seek unpublished results and data. We will contact researchers with expertise relevant to the review topic and EPOC interventions. We will conduct cited reference searches for all included studies in Science Citation Index, Web of Science.</p>
<p>All protocols will have this text – it can be added above the Grey literature heading.</p>	<p>We will provide all strategies used, including a list of sources screened and relevant reviews and primary studies reviewed.</p>

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

REVIEWS

Where in the review?	Abstract Search methods
Preferred reporting for abstract of review – edit as required.	<p>We searched CENTRAL, MEDLINE, Embase, x other databases and two trials registers on DD Month YYYY together with reference checking, citation searching and contact with study authors to identify additional studies.</p> <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add a date after each database name or provide a range of search dates, e.g. We searched between 25 July and 2 August 2016 (be careful to use dates in line with the Cochrane Style Manual, i.e. DD Month YYYY)</p>

Where in the review?	Main text
All reviews will have this text as these are the core databases that comply with MECIR.	<p>Search methods for identification of studies Electronic searches</p> <p>The EPOC Information Specialist developed the search strategies in consultation with the review authors.</p>
Check URLs are linked.	<p>We searched the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) and Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) for related systematic reviews on DD Month YYYY. We searched the following databases for primary studies on DD Month YYYY:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL; latest issue), in the Cochrane Library; • MEDLINE Ovid (report segment used, e.g. Ovid MEDLINE ALL 1946 to DD Month YYYY) • Embase Ovid (report segment used) • <i>etc</i> <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p>
For reviews searching for randomized trials only.	<p>Search strategies are comprised of natural language and controlled vocabulary terms. We applied no limits on language or publication date. In databases where it was possible and appropriate, study design filters for randomized trials were used; in MEDLINE we used a modified version of the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity- and precision-maximizing version (2008 revision) Lefebvre 2021. Limits were used in CINAHL and Embase to remove MEDLINE records in order to avoid duplication in downloaded results. Remaining results were deduplicated in EndNote against each other. All search strategies used are provided in Appendix 1.</p>
Report here if the searches were peer reviewed.	
For reviews searching for randomized trials and other study designs.	<p>Search strategies are comprised of natural language and controlled vocabulary terms. We applied no limits on language or publication date. In databases where it was possible and appropriate, study design filters were used to limit to the study designs of interest. For randomized trials in MEDLINE we used a modified version of the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity- and precision-maximizing version (2008 revision) Lefebvre 2021 with additional terms for other relevant study designs. Limits were used in CINAHL and Embase to remove MEDLINE records in order to avoid duplication in downloaded results. Remaining results were deduplicated in EndNote against each other. All search strategies used are provided in Appendix 1.</p>
Report here if the searches were peer reviewed.	

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

<p>All reviews will have this text (these two trials registries are mandatory in MECIR)</p>	<p>Searching other resources</p> <p>Trial registries</p> <p>We searched the following Trial registries on DD Month YYYY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHO ICTRP (World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform); trialssearch.who.int/ • US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register, ClinicalTrials.gov; clinicaltrials.gov/ <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p>
<p>Reviews may use some of this text. Report what was done for your review.</p> <p>A further explanation of methods may be needed if citation searching is conducted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which citations were searched? • When? • What interface and what database were used? 	<p>Grey literature</p> <p>We searched the grey literature to identify studies not indexed in the databases listed above on DD Month YYYY.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source, URL • Source, URL • <i>etc</i> <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p> <p>We also</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reviewed reference lists of all included studies and relevant systematic reviews for additional potentially eligible primary studies • contacted authors of included studies and reviews to clarify reported published information, and to seek unpublished results and data • contacted researchers with expertise relevant to the review topic and EPOC interventions • conducted cited reference searches on DD Month YYYY for all included studies in the following databases provided by Web of Science, Clarivate (e.g. Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) 1987 to present, Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) 1987 to present, etc.)
<p>All reviews will have this text – ensure Appendix is linked.</p>	<p>All strategies used are provided in Appendix 1.</p>

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

UPDATES

Where in the review?	Abstract Search methods
Preferred reporting for abstract of review – edit as required.	<p>We searched CENTRAL, MEDLINE, Embase, x other databases and two trials registers on DD Month YYYY together with reference checking, citation searching and contact with study authors to identify additional studies.</p> <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add a date after each database name or provide a range of search dates, e.g. We searched between 25 July and 2 August 2016 (be careful to use dates in line with the Cochrane Style Manual, i.e. DD Month YYYY)</p>

Where in the update?	Main text
All updates will have this text	<p>Search methods for identification of studies</p> <p>Electronic searches</p> <p>The EPOC Information Specialist developed the search strategies in consultation with the review authors.</p>
<p>For updates with revisions to search methods please report both here and under the review heading: “Differences between protocol and review”.</p> <p>This is an example of text that might be included in the methods. Report what was done.</p> <p>Cite the previous version of the review.</p>	<p>The searches were completely revised for this update by analysing the 30 included studies from the previous version of the review. The titles and abstracts were analysed for terms using both TerMine and Voyant Tools. Titles, abstracts and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) were analysed using the Yale MeSH Analyzer.</p> <p>New relevant MeSH added to MEDLINE since the last review version have been added to the search.</p>
<p>All updates have this text as these are the core databases that comply with MECIR.</p> <p>Check URLs are linked.</p>	<p>We searched the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR) and Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) for related systematic reviews on DD Month YYYY. We searched the following databases for primary studies on DD Month YYYY:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL; latest issue), in the Cochrane Library; • MEDLINE Ovid (report segment used, e.g. Ovid MEDLINE ALL 1946 to DD Month YYYY) • Embase Ovid (report segment used) • <i>etc</i> <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p>

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

<p>Updates searched for randomized trials only.</p> <p>Add dates. Amend text if all dates searched for the update.</p> <p>Report here if the searches were peer reviewed.</p>	<p>Search strategies are comprised of natural language and controlled vocabulary terms. We applied no limits on language. Searches were run from DD Month YYYY or YYYY onwards - the date of publication of the previous version of the review. In databases where it was possible and appropriate, study design filters for randomized trials were used; in MEDLINE we used a modified version of the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity- and precision-maximizing version (2008 revision) Lefebvre 2021. Limits were used in CINAHL and Embase to remove MEDLINE records in order to avoid duplication in downloaded results. Remaining results were deduplicated in EndNote against each other and against results from searches conducted in YYYY and YYYY for previous version(s) of the review. All search strategies used in this version of the review are provided in Appendix 1. Search strategies and search methods used in previous versions of the review are published within those prior publications.</p>
<p>Updates searched for randomized trials and other study designs.</p> <p>Add dates. Amend text if all dates searched for the update.</p> <p>Report here if the searches were peer reviewed.</p>	<p>Search strategies are comprised of natural language and controlled vocabulary terms. We applied no limits on language. Searches were run from DD Month YYYY or YYYY onwards - the date of publication of the previous version of the review. In databases where it was possible and appropriate, study design filters were used; for randomized trials in MEDLINE we used a modified version of the Cochrane Highly Sensitive Search Strategy for identifying randomized trials in MEDLINE: sensitivity- and precision-maximizing version (2008 revision) Lefebvre 2021 with additional terms for other relevant study designs. Limits were used in CINAHL and Embase to remove MEDLINE records in order to avoid duplication in downloaded results. Remaining results were deduplicated in EndNote against each other and against results from searches conducted in YYYY and YYYY for previous version(s) of the review. All search strategies used in this version of the review used are provided in Appendix 1. Search strategies and search methods used in previous versions of the review are published within those prior publications.</p>
<p>All updates (these two trials are mandatory in MECIR).</p>	<p>Searching other resources</p> <p>Trial registries</p> <p>We searched the following Trial registries on DD Month YYYY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHO ICTRP (World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform); trialsearch.who.int/ • US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register, ClinicalTrials.gov; clinicaltrials.gov/ <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p>
<p>Updates will use some of this text. Edit it depending on what was done.</p> <p>A further explanation of methods is likely to be needed if citation searching is conducted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which citations were searched? • When? • What interface and what database were used? 	<p>Grey literature</p> <p>We searched the grey literature to identify studies not indexed in the databases listed above on DD Month YYYY.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Source, URL • Source, URL • etc <p>Note: If searches conducted on different dates add (searched DD Month YYYY) after each database name.</p> <p>We also</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reviewed reference lists of all included studies and relevant systematic reviews for additional potentially eligible primary studies

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contacted authors of included studies and reviews to clarify reported published information, and to seek unpublished results and data • contacted researchers with expertise relevant to the review topic and EPOC interventions • conducted cited reference searches on DD Month YYYY for all included studies in the following databases provided by Web of Science, Clarivate (e.g. Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) 1987 to present, Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) 1987 to present, etc.)
<p>All updates to have this text – ensure Appendix is linked.</p>	<p>All strategies used are provided in Appendix 1.</p>

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

PRISMA flow diagram examples

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

A PRISMA flow diagram for a review update has an additional box stating the number of studies carried forward for inclusion from the previous version with a citation to that previous version as in the example below.

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

Examples of how to cite selected databases and resources

Please note not all these sources will be searched for every review.

Finding existing reviews	
CDSR	Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR; YYYY, Issue x) in the Cochrane Library
Epistemonikos	Epistemonikos, Epistemonikos Foundation (www.epistemonikos.org)
Health evidence	Health Evidence healthevidence.org/
Health systems evidence	Health Systems Evidence www.healthsystemsevidence.org/
Core databases	
CENTRAL	Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL; YYYY, Issue x) in the Cochrane Library
MEDLINE (OVID)	MEDLINE, Ovid (report segment used, e.g. Ovid MEDLINE ALL 1946 to DD Month YYYY)
Embase (OVID)	Embase, Ovid (report segment used, e.g. 1974 to DD Month YYYY)
Citation search	
Science Citation Index	Web of Science Core Collection, Science Citation Index Expanded, Clarivate (1900 to present)
Trials registries	
ClinicalTrials.gov	US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register, ClinicalTrials.gov; clinicaltrials.gov/
WHO ICTRP	WHO ICTRP (World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform); trialssearch.who.int/
Additional databases	
CINAHL	CINAHL EBSCO (Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature; 1980 to present)
SCOPUS	SCOPUS, Elsevier
Global Index Medicus	Global Index Medicus, World Health Organization (pesquisa.bvsalud.org/gim/advanced/?lang=en)
Virtual Health Library	VHL Regional Portal, Virtual Health Library (pesquisa.bvsalud.org/portal/advanced/?lang=en)
ERIC	ERIC ProQuest (1966 to DD Month YYYY) OR ERIC EBSCO (1966 to DD Month YYYY)
Global Health	Global Health, Ovid (1973 to present)
PsycINFO	PsycINFO Ovid (1987 to DD Month YYYY)
Sociological Abstracts	Sociological Abstracts, ProQuest (1952 to present)
LILACS	LILACS, Virtual Health Library (VHL) (Latin American and Caribbean Health Science Information database; 1982 to DD Month YYYY)
Grey Literature	
International HTA database	International HTA Database database.inahta.org/
BASE	BASE, Bielefeld University Library www.base-search.net/Search/Advanced
OpenGrey (archived 2021)	OpenGrey: doi.org/10.17026/dans-xtf-47w5

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

Grey Literature Report (discontinued 2017)	Grey Literature Report (New York Academy of Medicine): www.greylit.org/
AHRQ	Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ): www.ahrq.gov/
Joanna Briggs	Joanna Briggs Institute: www.joannabriggs.edu.au/Search.aspx
NICE	National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE): www.nice.org.uk/
Eldis	Eldis: www.eldis.org/

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

PRISMA-S Checklist and reporting the search process in EPOC reviews

Section/topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location(s) reported in EPOC reviews
INFORMATION SOURCES AND METHODS			
Database name	1	Name each individual database searched, stating the platform for each.	Search methods; search strategy appendix
Multi-database searching	2	If databases were searched simultaneously on a single platform, state the name of the platform, listing all of the databases searched.	Search methods; search strategy appendix
Study registries	3	List any study registries searched.	Search methods; search strategy appendix
Online resources and browsing	4	Describe any online or print source purposefully searched or browsed (e.g., tables of contents, print conference proceedings, web sites), and how this was done.	Search methods; search strategy appendix
Citation searching	5	Indicate whether cited references or citing references were examined, and describe any methods used for locating cited/citing references (e.g., browsing reference lists, using a citation index, setting up email alerts for references citing included studies).	Search methods; search strategy appendix
Contacts	6	Indicate whether additional studies or data were sought by contacting authors, experts, manufacturers, or others.	Search methods
Other methods	7	Describe any additional information sources or search methods used.	Search methods
SEARCH STRATEGIES			
Full search strategies	8	Include the search strategies for each database and information source, copied and pasted exactly as run.	Search strategy appendix
Limits and restrictions	9	Specify that no limits were used, or describe any limits or restrictions applied to a search (e.g., date or time period, language, study design) and provide justification for their use.	Search methods
Search filters	10	Indicate whether published search filters were used (as originally designed or modified), and if so, cite the filter(s) used.	Search methods
Prior work	11	Indicate when search strategies from other literature reviews were adapted or reused for a substantive part or all of the search, citing the previous review(s).	Search methods
Updates	12	Report the methods used to update the search(es) (e.g., rerunning searches, email alerts).	Search methods

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)

Dates of searches	13	For each search strategy, provide the date when the last search occurred.	Search methods
PEER REVIEW			
Peer review	14	Describe any search peer review process.	Search methods
MANAGING RECORDS			
Total records	15	Document the total number of records identified from each database and other information sources.	PRISMA flow diagram
Deduplication	16	Describe the processes and any software used to deduplicate records from multiple database searches and other information sources.	Search methods

Adapted from:

Table 1 PRISMA-S checklist in Rethlefsen, M.L., Kirtley, S., Waffenschmidt, S. *et al.* PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews. *Syst Rev* **10**, 39 (2021).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z>

Suggested citation: Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC). How to report the search process in EPOC protocols, reviews and review updates. EPOC Resources for review authors, 2021. epoc.cochrane.org/resources/epoc-resources-review-authors (accessed DD Month YYYY)